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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we report a novel approach based on a lensless Synthetic Optical Holography (SOH) that is aimed to recover the complex scattered field from buried surfaces at different wavelengths with sub-nanometric spectral resolution, without affecting the phase retrieval in depth. The proposed technique is applied to characterize and image the field scattered from a rough embedded surface of a microfluidic channel. The real and imaginary part of the random complex field revealed the presence of 2D optical vortices at each location in which a phase singularity is located. A statistical study of optical vortices is presented and the high spectral resolution is exploited to study the behavior of topological charges with the frequency shift.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic Optical Holography (SOH) is a technique recently introduced with the aim to combine Digital Off-axis Holography (DOH) and Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM). The former is a well-known imaging technique, able to retrieve the complex scattered field from a sample, by measuring a single hologram acquired by a CCD camera.¹⁻³ In DOH, the hologram is generated by means of the interference between the coherent scattered light from a sample and a reference wave, incident with a tilted angle on the recording sensor.⁴ This angular misalignment introduces a linear spatial modulation in the phase of the reference wave and consequently in the intensity distribution of the recorded hologram. The information relative to the complex scattered field can be directly recovered by filtering and demodulating the high spatial frequency components of the acquired interference pattern.⁴ This method has found wide application in metrology and in many fields of physics,^{5,6} as well as in some more recent paper for Lab-on-chip applications.⁷ On the other side,

Scanning Probe Microscopy includes different techniques and some of these were recently combined with DOH,⁸ borrowing from Microwave Holography, the concept of Synthetic Reference Wave already introduced in Synthetic Aperture Radars.⁹ In the frame of SPM techniques, novel approaches are also gaining interest. In particular, optical scanning micro cavities have been applied, thanks to their high sensitivity, for enhanced Raman spectroscopy, nano-particle detection and imaging.¹⁰⁻¹² After a recent implementation of SOH through a lens free configuration,¹³ in the present work we demonstrate its integration with Optical Tomography to retrieve quantitative phase information from the scattered fields of embedded surfaces. In the past, digital holography was combined with a full-field OCT system working in a Fourier-domain, demonstrating a depth-independent lateral resolution.³ Here, without using tunable light sources and working on a wide bandwidth, we exploit the high sensitivity of a scanning lens-free optical probe in a common-path configuration fed by a SLED source.

II. THE TECHNIQUE

As reported in Fig. 1, the intensity $I(\mathbf{r}, \lambda)$, recorded point-by-point by the Optical Spectrum Analyzer, is shaped by reflections inside the cavity and by the interference of diffracted waves from the fiber facet.

It can be modeled as described in Ref. 14 by the relation:

$$I(\lambda, \mathbf{r}) = |A(\lambda)|^2 \frac{1 - 2\text{Re}\{\gamma(\lambda, \mathbf{r})\}}{1 + 2\text{Re}\{\gamma(\lambda, \mathbf{r})\}} \quad (1)$$

in which $|A(\lambda)|^2$ is the power spectral density of source laser and $\text{Re}\{\gamma(\lambda, \mathbf{r})\}$ is the interference term, whose phase $\phi(\mathbf{r})$ is dependent on the complex field $U_S(\lambda, \mathbf{r}) = e^{j\alpha(\lambda, \mathbf{r})}$ scattered from the sample and related to its topography and permittivity (see Eq. 2). The above relation was derived assuming a linearly polarized mode propagating inside a single mode optical fiber. The coherence of the wavefront incident on the sample is ensured by the small fiber core (Mode Field Diameter = $5.6\mu\text{m}$) and the probe-sample distance, according to the Van Cittert-Zernike's theorem.¹⁵ The principle of SOH is based on the concept that it is possible to mimic a DOH system in a scanning microscope, by synthesizing a linear spatial modulation inside the phase of the interference term (linear with respect to the direction of the probe displacement).⁸ In the proposed configuration, a phase modulation is implemented by changing with a constant velocity the optical cavity dimension $d(r)$, while the sample is scanned along the lateral direction r ,¹³ as reported in Fig. 1(c):

$$\begin{aligned} d(r) &= d_0 - \tan\theta \cdot r + d_{\text{sample}}(r) \\ \phi(r) &= \beta(k_r)d = \beta(k_r)d_0 - \beta(k_r)\tan\theta \cdot r - \alpha(k_r, r)/2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. 2, d_0 is a reference distance, $d_{\text{sample}}(r)$ is the sample topography and the angle θ describes the synthetic tilted plane, inducing a linear modulation equal to $\beta(k_r) \cdot \tan\theta \cdot r$

inside the phase $\phi(r)$, for each radial spatial frequency k_r . The angle θ must be chosen considering that the spatial modulation frequency is constrained inside a range, whose limits are defined by the bandwidth f_{max} of the acquired signal and the spatial sampling frequency of the scanning system, depending on the number of scanning points N used to image the hologram over a scanning window L :

$$\left(\frac{f_{\text{max}} \cdot \lambda}{2\pi}\right) \leq \tan\theta \leq \left(\frac{N \cdot \lambda}{4L \cdot \pi}\right) \quad (3)$$

The bandwidth f_{max} is determined by the spatial resolution of the scanning probe used to acquire the hologram, which is in turn limited by the NA of optical fiber. Once the modulation frequency is defined, by exploiting the low-coherence feature of the optical source, it is possible to compute the scattering intensity profile in depth for each scanning point and encode inside a hologram the information relative to the field scattered from each buried layer, as highlighted in Fig. 2. In this configuration the relation for each wavelength λ between the scattered field U_S and the interference term $\text{Re}\{\gamma(\lambda, \mathbf{r})\}$ reported in Ref. 13 can be rewritten as:

$$2\text{Re}\{\gamma(\lambda, \mathbf{r})\} = \frac{2\text{Re}\{G(\lambda, \mathbf{r})\}}{1 + |G(\lambda, \mathbf{r})|^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} G(\lambda, x, y, z) &= \left\langle \rho \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1} \{ \tilde{U}_S^n(q - 2nq_R, x, y, z) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \tilde{U}_S^n(q + 2nq_R, x, y, z) \} \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In Eq. 5 the brackets denote the integration along the radial spatial frequency q , whereas $\tilde{U}_S^n(q, \lambda)$ is the Two-Dimensional spatial Fourier Transform of the field U_S , scattered from each layer z in depth. The term $2nq_R$ represents the transverse spatial modulation frequency related to the n -th order spectrum \tilde{U}_S^n . Finally, the pre-multiplicative factor ρ is equal to

FIG. 1. (a) Experimental set-up, (b) details about the scanning probe, (c) implementation of SOH by means of a synthetic tilted plane, described by the angle θ , equal to the ratio between the scan size along r direction and the total displacement along z direction. An optical extrinsic Fabry-Perot cavity is used as a scanning probe (NA = 0.10-0.14 and Mode Field Diameter equal to $5.6\mu\text{m}$) fed by a broadband super-luminescent diode laser (SLED) at 850 nm (power 0.6 mW , bandwidth FWHM 40 nm). The micro-cavity is established as Fabry-Perot interference between the reflection(s) from the sample and the light reflected by the facet back into the fiber. The back-reflected spectrum is acquired by means of an Optical Spectrum Analyzer (OSA), while the sample is placed on a piezoelectric scanner.

FIG. 2. (a) Point-by-point the reflected spectrum is acquired whilst the sample is moving along the normal z direction with constant velocity, (b) back-reflected spectrum shaped by the reflections coming from all the embedded layers, (c) scattering intensity profile in depth, computed by applying the spatial IFFT to the acquired spectrum, (d) spectra relative to the selected layer retrieved by applying the spatial FFT to the filtered portion of signal, (e) For each wavelength λ^* , within the source bandwidth, the interference term $\text{Re}[\gamma(\lambda^*, r)]$ is recorded, mapping a hologram for the selected buried layer, (f) 2D spatial FFT of the recorded holograms. Filtering the spectrum in the spatial frequency domain requires that the spatial modulating frequency of the hologram and the sampling frequency of the image must satisfy the relation described in Eq. 3.

$[H_0(e_0)]^2 \beta(q) / \beta_0$, being $H_0(e_0)$ the Hankel transform of the fiber guided mode e_0 with β_0 and $\beta(q)$ the longitudinal spatial frequencies of guided mode and scattered fields, respectively.¹³ Assuming that the distance between each interface is greater than the coherence length of the source, the acquired spectrum will be shaped by all reflections coming from each buried layer, like in a sequence of multiple independent optical cavities (see Fig. 2(b)). For each scanning point, the scattering profile is analyzed in order to extract the signal coming from each buried surface. The embedded layers are filtered by applying the Hann window function centered on each scattering point, according to the geometry reported in Fig. 3(a) and avoiding peaks due to the multiple reflections (the dashed blue lines in Fig. 2(c) describe the bandwidth of the filter). In addition, the window function must have a spatial width much larger

than the coherence length of the source in order to avoid distortion of the retrieved signal. A new set of holograms relative to the selected layer is obtained (see Fig. 2(e)) for each wavelength within the source bandwidth, with just a single scan. The limits of the wavelength range $\lambda_1 - \lambda_n$ reported in Fig. 2(d), are chosen so that to avoid the overlapping with the extremes of the wavelengths range of the source, where the random fluctuations of the intensity could affect in a more relevant way the retrieved hologram in term of noise. A subnanometric spectral resolution equal to 0.1 nm is achieved (due to the resolution of the OSA) without affecting the phase retrieval in depth. It is relevant to highlight that the high spectral sensitivity is obtained due to the idea of implementing Synthetic Holography in frequency domain, instead of time domain.⁸ The complex scattered field is obtained by filtering

FIG. 3. Micro fluidic channel realized by means of a femtosecond laser pulse machine, (a) Optical microscope image (uncertainty $\pm 3 \mu\text{m}$) relative to the cross-section of the channel. The dimensions of the channel are in good agreement with the scattering profile in Fig. 2(c). According to that, the first layer is located around $d_1 = 365 \mu\text{m}$, the second interface is placed around $d_2 = 530 \mu\text{m}$ whereas the thickness of the channel under test is about $d_1 - d_2 = 165 \mu\text{m}$. Assuming the refractive index of glass is around 1.451, the first layer is located around $d_1 = 251 \mu\text{m}$, (b) topography of the top surface under test, realized by scanning the equivalent open surface by means of Atomic Force Microscope.

and demodulating the high spatial frequency components of the hologram, centered on the 1st order of the modulation frequency. In fact, due to the resonant behavior of the micro cavity, higher modulation frequencies are present (see Fig. 2(f)). The bandwidth of the filter, applied in the spatial frequency domain to demodulate the signal (see Fig. 2(f)), is determined by the numerical aperture of the scanning probe.¹³ When all the aforementioned conditions are fulfilled, the complex field can be extracted, providing a lateral resolution equal to about $1 \mu\text{m}$.^{3,13}

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

With the aim to prove the capability of the technique in extracting quantitative phase information in depth, we computed the magnitude and phase of the field scattered from a random rough surface of a glass-buried microfluidic channel. The microfluidic guide was obtained by a Femtosecond Laser Irradiation followed by Chemical Etching (FLICE) technique,¹⁶ as imaged in Fig. 3. This is an interesting case in which a phase imaging of the random scattered field can allow to highlight the presence and behavior of optical vortices in depth. It is known, in fact, that when a coherent light is scattered from a surface with a random topography, due to the interference between the random plane waves, a speckled pattern is generated with regions having higher and lower brightness.^{17,18} The latter areas are characterized by a partial or complete cancellation of the scattered field. In those points in which zero intensity occurs, both the real and imaginary parts of the scattered fields are simultaneously zero and the phase of the field is undefined.

These locations are characterized by a phase singularity or wavefront dislocation and are related to the presence of localized optical vortices.¹⁹ These particular features were observed for the first time in Ref. 20 and during the last years they were widely modeled and studied. More recently, phase singularities were imaged inside speckle patterns by exploiting super-resolution techniques²¹ and measured by a

space-variant half-wave plate.²² The presence of optical vortices occurs under well-defined conditions that uniquely define them in a speckled pattern.¹⁷ These conditions have been investigated in the complex field reported in Fig. 4, scattered from a buried rough surface (see Fig. 3). Importantly, these conditions cannot be studied just by acquiring the topography or contrast phase imaging.²³ In detail, for a fully-developed speckle, the real and imaginary parts of the scattered field are zero-mean Gaussian random variables and in order to have a zero of intensity, both the real part and the imaginary parts of the field must be zero at the same point in space (see Fig. 5(d)). These intersections are points of singularities for the phase and define the center of optical vortex. Although at these positions, the phase of scattered field is undefined, in close proximity of these points, the phase distribution has interesting properties.¹⁷

According to the way in which the zero contour lines of real and imaginary parts intersect each other, the phase around a singularity can circulate in two different ways, namely: clockwise (negative vortex) and counterclockwise (positive vortex). These two types of vortex circulation led to the concept of topological charge that defines the number of times the phase increases/decreases by 2π moving around a singularity (see Fig. 5(b)). Another interesting property of optical vortices, called sign principle, is highlighted in Fig. 5, according to which, on a zero contour of either real or imaginary parts, adjacent vortices have opposite sign. This feature is related to the property of the conservation of topological charge.¹⁷

A further characteristic, experimentally investigated in few works,^{24,25} is the behavior of topological charges with frequency shift. This aspect is attracting great interest, as it was observed that when varying the wavelength of a random wave, phase singularities exhibit the Brownian statistics of a random walk.²⁴ This example also allows to highlight the sub-nanometric spectral sensitivity of the system in tomographic phase imaging at different wavelengths. This feature is depicted in Fig. 6 (Multimedia view), in which it is reported

FIG. 4. (a) Normalized magnitude and (b) unwrapped phase of the scattered field from the embedded microfluidic top surface. (c) Normalized magnitude and (d) unwrapped phase of the scattered field from microfluidic bottom surface.

FIG. 5. (a) Wrapped and (b) unwrapped phase of the complex scattered field from the top surface. In (b) the green line is the real part whereas the red line is the imaginary part. In each intersection is highlighted the sense of circulation of the vortex, (c) normalized magnitude of the scattered field, (d) zero contour lines of real and imaginary parts. The dots in the pictures define the position of optical vortex (positive and negative charges).

the contour zero lines of the real and imaginary parts of the complex scattered field at different wavelengths. Although the zero contour lines of real and imaginary parts change their shape quite fast accordingly to the variation of wavelength, the position of the topological charges are quite stable and in some point it is also possible to observe their creation after a change in wavelengths (see Fig. 6 (Multimedia view)). In mapping the evolution of the contour lines in Fig. 6 (Multimedia view), we have chosen a small range of wavelengths located inside the source bandwidth in which the noise related to the source fluctuations was low. As mentioned before, such a

small shift of wavelengths led to a quite stable speckle pattern configuration.

This is also confirmed by comparing the spectral correlation width of the random scattered field (around 40 nm), with the range of wavelengths considered in the analysis (around 5 nm).²⁶ The recorded speckle pattern, was analyzed by evaluating the spatial density of optical vortices per unit area, defined as $1/(2A_{\text{coh}})$.¹⁷ The physical quantity A_{coh} is the coherence area of the speckled pattern or, in other words, the intensity correlation area related to the correlation length of the Gaussian random wavefield. According to the image reported

FIG. 6. Contour-zero lines of the real and imaginary parts of the complex scattered field from the top surface at different wavelengths, (a) 840.1 nm, (b) 837.7 nm, (c) 836.4 nm, (d) 835.8 nm. The arrows in each figure highlight the creation and diffusion of topological charges ± 1 (Optical Spectrum Analyzer resolution ≈ 0.1 nm). Multimedia view: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5053564.1>

in Fig. 4(b), the number of vortices appearing over a scanning area of $100 \times 60 \mu\text{m}^2$ is about 96, giving a spatial density of vortices equal to $1.6 \pm 0.04 \cdot (10^{-2})\mu\text{m}^{-2}$. This result is in good agreement with the theoretical value equal to about $1.57 \cdot 10^{-2}\mu\text{m}^{-2}$ (as reported in Ref. 17), having measured a correlation length of the Gaussian random field equal to about $3.18 \mu\text{m}$. In summary, we have demonstrated tomographic and depth-invariant phase imaging with sub-nanometric spectral resolution by combining SOH with Optical Tomography at micro scale, implemented through a lens-free and noninvasive approach. Although this feature has been described in a quite narrow bandwidth – with a single mode optical fiber used as scanning probe – the same concept could be extended and applied to a wider bandwidth by using white light source and multi-mode optical fiber as a probe. That could pave the way towards hyper-spectral imaging and optical spectroscopy in depth, by means of a non-invasive technique, suitable for biological applications. In addition to that, the system could also be applied, in principle, to turbid media thanks to its high sensitivity to low-intensity backscattered signals. This feature is due to its common path optical and interferometric configuration.

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